

Effects of Class-Size on Retention in Chemistry Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects of class-size on retention in chemistry concepts among Senior Secondary School Chemistry Students in Zaria Local Government Area, Kaduna State. Four research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental. The target population was all senior secondary school class two (SSSII) chemistry students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kaduna state. The sample size for this study were one hundred and fifty (150) secondary school II chemistry students randomly selected from three secondary schools in Zaria. The instrument used for data collection was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT). A reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained for the instrument using Pearson's Product-Moment correlation coefficient which implies that the instrument was reliable for the study. The data obtained through CAT were subjected to One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the hypotheses at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level. The results obtained revealed significant differences in the Post-Post test scores (F value is 32.08 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with df of 148). The results of the study showed, among others, that from individual class-size groupings, there was no significant difference in retention of subjects exposed to chemistry concepts and the retention of chemistry concepts favored all the subjects equally irrespective of the nature of the class-size. The researcher recommends that there should be continuous support for new researches in class-size and that information obtained could substantially improve the academic achievement and retention level of chemistry students.

Keywords: Class-size, Retention, Chemistry concepts, Chemistry students, Secondary school.

Introduction

It is imperative to define and give the historical origin of science and chemistry before discussing in detail, the effect class-size has on the academic achievement and retention of students in Chemistry. The origin and beginning of science could be as old as the beginning of human race, arising from the need of man to solve various problems that threatened his survival.

Science is a progressive activity that constitutes the world and permeates almost every aspect of modern life. Science seeks to explain how the universe operates and encompasses the natural, social and applied sciences. Science is basically concerned with the study of natural phenomena that can empirically be tested. Igboanugo and Egolum (2017) view science as the systematic investigation of nature with a view to understanding and harnessing them for human benefits. The aims of teaching science is to enable students understand, retain and use the knowledge obtained to solve problems through laboratory work, field work and class work. Most teachers unfortunately do not have the capacity to actualize these ideas since they are faced with prevailing students' excesses which often results in the disruption of class work, cheating and physical aggression. Chemistry is one of the three major basic sciences along with biology and physics. According to Achimugu (2017), chemistry as part of science and as a school subject, is made of concepts which require complex mental process that involves visualizing, manipulating, analyzing, abstracting and associating with idea. It is necessary to understand the material world in order to exploit its properties for the benefit of humanity. The study of chemistry is very important to mankind and also in the following areas of human life: Agriculture, Textiles, Pharmaceutical Industries, Polymer industries Medicine. The teaching of Chemistry involves developing basic chemistry skills which include observation, manipulation, classification, inference, hypothesizing, interpreting data, formulating model. In addition, the skills and knowledge gained through chemistry should be applied in solving everyday problems in the environment.

The general poor academic achievement of students in chemistry was what motivated the present scholar to undertake a research on the effect of class-size on the academic achievement and retention of learned concepts in chemistry among secondary school students with the aim of finding solutions which will go a long way in improving the retention level of students who write chemistry in the senior school certificate examination (SSCE).

A class is identified as a course/section combination with one or more teachers scheduled in a particular room, in a particular school, in a specific term, during a specific period and day of the week. According to FSIR (2003-04), class-size is determined by bringing the total number of students in the classroom and dividing by the number of teachers assigned to the

students. On the issue of how average class-size differs from a student teacher ratio, FSIR (2003-04) has indicated that student teacher ratio is derived by merely dividing the number of school students in membership by the number of staff who are classified as teachers in the school. They argued that student/teacher ratio does not account for the number of classes taught during the day or how many students are assigned to each of the classes. On the other hand average class-size is based on counts of students assigned to specific classes. Wikipedia (2015) refers class-size to be the number of students a teacher faces during a given period of instruction.

Eboatu and Ehirim (2018) define class-size as the number of students a teacher attends to during a given period of instruction.. Class size is thus different from the student-teacher ratio, which is expressed as the relationship between the student population and the number of teachers available in the school. Resnick (2018) stressed that class size must be reduced substantially to achieve the benefits. A large class-size is the ratio of one teacher to fifty students (1:50) and above. Liz and Lisa (2022) noted that the numerical strength of the class does not permit the teacher to cope effectively with the demands of the individual student. They further noted that the individual student is buried in the group as a result of the largeness of the class. More so, uniform instructional technique is used in reaching out to all the students with different abilities at the same time. Filges, Sonne-Schmidt and Bjørn (2018) concluded that reducing class size from 40 or more to 20 pupils led to almost no increase in achievement. Not until class size is being dropped to 15pupils or lower will there be larger effects on achievement. Teachmint, (2024) indicated that class-size refers to the total number of students in each classroom. Depending upon class-size, teachers divide the students by making an active learning classroom where they engage the students in deep learning.

In this study, class-size is defined as the total number of students in a class at a given time. Specifically, small class-size is defined as one teacher to handle twenty five (25) students (1:25); average class-size is seen as a teacher having fifty (50) students (1:50), while a large class-size is defined as one teacher to handle seventy five (75) students (1:75). This is formulated by the researcher for the purpose of this study.

A study conducted in the field of teaching and learning using various class-sizes that does not take cognizance of retention of materials/knowledge taught is not complete. Retention therefore forms an integral part of this study to establish the differences in academic achievement of students in various class-sizes and level of retention of chemistry concepts. Apparently, few research works have been conducted in this area of retention; some of such studies were Azigwe, Kyriakides, Panayiot and Creemers (2016), they reviewed a study on the link between student engagement and class size, and they revealed that students' engagement behavior and retention are affected seriously by the class size. They indicated that when students were placed in smaller classes they became more engaged academically and socially. Also, with strong social academic engagement, academic attachment and retention improved. The ability to solve any problem or even to recognize that a problem exists depends on memory. Practice or review tends to build and maintain memory for a task or any learned material. Britannica Encyclopedia (2003) stated that in measuring retention, the rate tends to vary with the methods used and they are basically those of recall, recognition and relearning.

The retention level of the subjects in the various class-sizes taught chemistry concepts were investigated in this study. The aim is to determine which group of students showed higher retention levels of the materials learnt. This study would therefore, serve as a reference point for further studies.

The study of Chemistry at the Secondary School level is not only to give students the opportunity to manipulate apparatus and enquire meaningful learning but also to develop basic chemistry skills which include observation, classification, inference, hypothesizing, interpreting and formulating data among others. The Secondary School students are also to develop self-confidence and reliance through problem solving activities. Liz and Lisa (2022) have shown that large classes have the tendency of limiting the achievement of mediocre students in Mathematics since high ability students will always dominate in such classes.

The problem of this study is therefore, to substantiate the effect of class-size on retention by students as it affects their academic achievement in Chemistry when exposed to guided discovery method of teaching.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.
2. Determine any difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts.
3. Examine any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.

4. Find any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size

Research Questions

1. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach?
2. Is there any difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts?
3. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach?
4. Is there any difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size when taught chemistry concepts?

Hypotheses

To answer the stated research questions, the following null hypotheses were formulated.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State.
3. **H₀₃**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State.
4. **H₀₄**: There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach among secondary school students in Zaria, Kaduna State.

Methodology

The study is quasi-experimental research design investigating the effect of different class-sizes on the level of retention of chemistry students in secondary schools in Zaria Nigeria. The research was a comparative study of three groups of varying class-sizes. The target population was Senior Secondary School II chemistry students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria, had thirteen Secondary Schools with a total number of 2,307 chemistry students. The samples for this study were one hundred and fifty (150) SS11 chemistry students drawn randomly from three secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis, in Kaduna State. The three secondary schools were randomly selected with respect to the fact that the schools had covered substantial content/topics in the SSSCE chemistry syllabus. In each of the three schools, one formed the small class-size, the second one formed the average class-size and the third school formed the large class-size. This division into various class-sizes of 25, 50 and 75 was done by stratified random sampling to ensure that every student had equal chance of participating actively in the study. All the students in the three different schools were taught chemistry concept using the guided discovery approach,

The instrument used was Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) developed by the researcher and consist of thirty multiple choice chemistry test items. They were validated by a panel of experts that include two chemistry senior lecturers at a university, one science educator and two secondary school chemistry teachers. The multiple choice items referred to as the Chemistry Achievement Test were used at three different occasions:-First, as pre-test:- to determine the strength and equality of the samples at the start of the study. Secondly, as post-test in order to determine or assess the performance of the students after the treatment and later administered as post-posttest to determine their level of retention of learnt chemistry concepts.

A pilot testing with a sample of 50 students was conducted using the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) items on SSS II chemistry students of Government Secondary School other than the schools under study in Zaria. The reasons and benefits of pilot testing were to identify problems or difficulties that might arise before the final administration of the instruments to the study samples. The scores from three tests were correlated using Pearson's Product-Moment correlation coefficient and reliability coefficient of 0.74 was obtained.

The data obtained through CAT were subjected to One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to test the hypothesis at $P \leq 0.05$ significant level.

Presentation of Results

The pre-test scores were used to establish the equivalence of the three comparable groups (School A, B, and C) before the treatment. The pretest scores were subjected to a one-way analysis of variance and tested at a significant level of 0.05 as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: One-way Analysis of Variance of the Pre-test Mean Scores of Subjects in the Three Classes

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Df	Mean squares	Fcal	Fcrit	P	Remark
Between groups	14.43	2	7.21	1.71	3.05	0.18	NS
Within groups	617.95	147	4.20				
Total	632.37	149					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The obtained F-value (calculated) is 1.71. This value is less than the F- value critical which is 3.05 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with $df = 149$. The result shows that there was no statistically significant difference between the achievements of subjects in all the classes/groups. The P-value of 0.183 is also not significant thus implying group equivalence with respect to their knowledge of chemistry concepts before the exposure to treatment since the level of significance is 0.05.

Testing H_{01}

There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in large, medium and small class-sizes when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.

One way analysis of variance using SPSS 11.50 package was applied with a view to testing the hypothesis. The result is as presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Analysis of variance of Post-Post test scores comparing retention level of all the three groups

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F	P	Remarks
Between groups	422.60	2	211.30	32.08	0.000	S
Within groups	574.80	148	6.587			
Total	1397.40	150				

* Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The results in Table 2 show that the obtained F value is 32.08 at $\alpha = 0.05$ with df of 148. This implies that there is a significant difference in level of retention in the Post-Post test scores of all the three groups. All the subjects retained the chemistry concepts learnt. The null hypothesis is thus rejected since significant differences in level of retention exist.

H_{02} : There is no significant difference in the level of retention of students in large class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery strategy.

To test the level of retention of subjects in a large class size, data from the Post-Post test scores were collected from the subjects in large class size. One way analysis of variance was used. The result is shown in Table 3

Table 3: Comparison of the Post –Posttest mean scores of high, average and low ability groups in large class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value	Fcrit	Remark
Between groups	25.38	2	12.69	1.75	0.18	3.12	NS
Within groups	520.16	72	7.22				
Total	545.55	74					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The results (from Table 3) show that F value calculated 1.75 is less than the F critical 3.12 with $df = 74$ and P- value of 0.18 was obtained. The results indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of retention in large class-size. This implies that the subjects retained the learnt chemistry concepts equally.

To Test H_{03}

There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in medium class-size when taught chemistry concepts using guided discovery approach.

Mean scores of Post-Posttest of the high, average and low ability groups of students in the Medium class-size and these scores were computed using one way analysis of variance. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: One-way analysis of variance of the Post-Posttest mean scores of the high, average and low ability groups in medium class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value	Fcrit	Remark
Between groups	6.37	12.69	3.185	0.92	0.40	3.19	NS
Within groups	162.75	47	3.46				
Total	169.12	49					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

The obtained calculated F-value of 0.92 is less than critical F-value of 3.19 at $\alpha 0.05$ with $df = 49$. Results from Table 3 indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of chemistry concepts learnt in a class-size of 50. This means subjects in that class retained materials learnt equally.

To Test H_{04}

To test for significant difference in the level of retention of students in a small class-size, which states thus “there is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in small class-size”, one-way analysis of variance was used. Scores were obtained from Post-Posttest and the result is presented in Table5.

Table 5: One-way Analysis of the Post-Post test scores of the high, average and low ability groups in a small class-size

Source of variance	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	Fcal	P-value-	F crit	Remark
Between groups	44.30	2	22.15	2.25	0.12	3.44	NS
Within groups	215	22	9.80				
Total	260	24					

* Not significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 5.shows that the calculated F-value of 2.25 and critical F value of 3.44 with $df = 24$ was obtained. The P value of 0.12 at $\alpha = 0.05$ was not significant. The result implies that there is no significant difference in the level of retention of subjects (high, average and low ability levels of students) in the small class-size. In other words subjects within the group retained materials learnt equally.

Summary of Findings

1. There is significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts between students in small, medium and large class-sizes.
2. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concepts in large class-size.
3. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concept in medium class-size
4. There is no significant difference in the level of retention of selected chemistry concept in small class-size

Discussion of Findings

The objective of this study was to investigate the effects of class-size and the level of retention among Senior Secondary School chemistry Students. The results from testing the null hypothesis 1 revealed significant differences in the Post-Post test scores. All the subjects retained the taught concepts for a significantly longer period as shown in Table 2. However, results emanating from individual class-size grouping revealed that there was no significant difference in retention of subjects exposed to chemistry concepts (See Tables 3-5).

Retention of Chemistry concepts thus favoured all the subjects equally irrespective of the nature of the class-size. That is, each subject (student) in large, medium and small class-sizes retained the learnt concepts. But when the groups were compared with each other, small class-size was found to retain the learnt concepts the most among the three class-size groupings. Thus the research question “Is there significant difference in the level of retention among students in small, medium and large class-sizes is therefore answered in favour of the small class-size grouping. The level of retention recorded by small, medium (average) and large class-size grouping could be due to the instructional strategy that was used in teaching. This strategy enabled subjects in all the class-size groupings to be actively involved in the learning process where they were given the opportunity or expected to observe, hypothesize, classify, measure, analysis, experiment, manipulate as well as interpret data obtained. In the process of carrying out these processes, it appears that meaningful learning and subsequently greater

retention resulted. Thus the use of instructional strategy that improves retention in relation to class-size is advocated for. Many researchers such as Azigwe, Kyriakides, Panayiot and Creemers (2016) who reviewed a study on the link between student engagement and class size, revealed that students' engagement behavior and retention were affected seriously by the class size. The study indicated that when students were placed in smaller classes they become more engaged academically and socially. With strong social academic engagement, academic attachment and retention of concepts was improved.

Conclusion

The findings of this study therefore, suggest that chemistry teachers should emphasize those instructional strategies that are characterized by active and participatory learning such as guided discovery approach which leads to meaningful learning and understanding of concepts which is easily retained in the teaching of chemistry.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made on the basis of the findings and conclusions emanating from this study.

1. There should be continuous support for new researches in class-size.
2. Information obtained from researches could substantially improve academic achievement and retention level of students.
3. More studies should continuously be conducted to assess the effectiveness of class-size

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